

Before-and-After Assessment of Per Capita Income: Poverty Status among Agricultural Cooperative Members

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Abstract

Agricultural cooperatives are substantial in enhancing the livelihood of rural people and alleviating poverty in the developing countries. This paper aims to make before-and-after assessment of per capita income among agricultural cooperative members to determine their poverty status in the Hetauda Sub-Metropolitan City of Makawanpur District, Nepal. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design. It was conducted using primary data that were collected through structured questionnaire in 2025 from five agricultural cooperatives. A total of 123 members were randomly selected from a population of 180 participants. The analysis of household welfare changes with before and after strategy was based on indicators like per capita income, per capita expenditure, membership period and household size. The data were analyzed by using descriptive statistics, paired samples t-tests, and correlation analysis. Findings indicate that the average household income per capita grew by NPR 75,878 prior to the membership to NPR 124,946 upon joining the cooperative. The cooperative members were able to raise their economic status. The

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study is significant as it evaluates the prominent role of agricultural cooperatives in reducing poverty by comparing members' per capita income before and after participation.

Keywords: Agriculture cooperatives, Poverty, Poverty status, per capita income, Household income, Household expenditure

Introduction

Poverty has remained one of the most fundamental development issues in many developing nations, especially in rural agrarian economies where farming is a major source of livelihood for most households (Christiaensen & Kuhl, 2011; Ellis & Freeman, 2004). In such settings, lack of access to financial services, agricultural inputs, markets, and institutional support has often been a major limiting factor for productivity and income creation among farming households (Bhattarai & Pandit, 2023; Joshi, 2024). Rural poverty has thus remained a major problem in such settings due to inherent inequalities in resource distribution and market participation (Bharadwaj, 2012). Cooperative institutions have increasingly been identified as important institutional solutions to such challenges, as they improve access to credit, technology, and marketing opportunities for smallholder farmers (Risal, 2021; Dhakal, 2022). By promoting democratic ownership and collective action, cooperatives provide farmers with an important platform to improve their bargaining power and economic resilience (Chauguthi et al., 2023).

In Nepal, agriculture remains the backbone of the rural economy, employing a large proportion of the population and providing the primary livelihood for most rural households (Yogi et al., 2025). Despite improvements in national poverty reduction over the past decades, many rural communities continue to experience low agricultural productivity, unstable incomes, and limited financial inclusion (Bhattarai & Dahal, 2022). As a result, the Government of Nepal has emphasized cooperative development as an important strategy for rural development and poverty alleviation

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(Ministry of Land Management, Cooperatives and Poverty Alleviation, 2019). The cooperative sector has expanded rapidly, particularly after the policy reforms introduced in the early 1990s, with agricultural cooperatives playing a significant role in providing credit services, agricultural inputs, training, and market access to rural farmers (Dhakal, 2022; Risal, 2021). These institutions help overcome market failures and enhance farmers' ability to participate in economic activities that improve household welfare (Bharadwaj, 2012; Chauguthi et al., 2023).

Agricultural cooperatives are member-owned entities that seek to enhance the socioeconomic well-being of their members by facilitating joint production, savings, lending, and marketing efforts (Bhattarai & Pandit, 2023). Various studies carried out in Nepal have established that membership in cooperatives helps to enhance agricultural practices, income generation, and livelihood security for rural households (Dhakal, 2022; Dhakal, 2024). For example, studies on farmers' cooperatives have established that members of farmers' cooperatives usually enjoy better agricultural practices and access to agricultural inputs and subsidies, which in turn improve productivity and the socioeconomic status (Neupane et al., 2018) of members. On the other hand, empirical studies have established that there is a marked increase in the income of households that join cooperatives due to improved financial literacy and access to credit and marketing services (Dhakal & Mueser, 2023).

In addition to income generation, cooperatives also play a role in other aspects of rural development. Financial services offered through cooperatives enable households to invest in agriculture and earn income from other sources, hence improving their resilience to economic shocks (Joshi, 2024; Parajuli, 2024). Membership of cooperatives in Nepal has been shown to have a positive impact on the economic well-being of members due to improved access to financial services, market integration, and social networks in rural areas (Khadka, 2024; Bhattarai & Pandit,

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2023). This is an important role that cooperatives play in poverty reduction in developing countries (Joshi et al., 2021).

However, despite the rising importance of agricultural cooperatives in rural development, there is a lack of empirical research on the impact of agricultural cooperatives on household poverty, especially in relation to the estimation of changes in welfare levels. Many studies have focused on cross-sectional analysis between members and non-members of agricultural cooperatives, which might not reflect the changing levels of household welfare after membership (Verhofstadt & Maertens, 2015; Abate et al., 2013). The before-and-after approach, using variables such as income, expenditure, and size of household, provides a more complete analysis of the impact of membership in agricultural cooperatives on poverty status. Income measures productivity; expenditure measures welfare and living standards; while size of household measures dependency ratios and allocation of household resources (Haughton & Khandker, 2009).

The Makawanpur District in the Bagmati Province provides a relevant context in which to examine the impact of agricultural cooperatives on household poverty. Hetauda, the district headquarters, is surrounded by agricultural communities in which cooperatives are actively engaged in offering financial services, agricultural inputs, and training for farmers. However, studies on cooperative management in Makawanpur suggest that there are institutional challenges to transparency, accountability, and member participation that could influence the extent to which cooperatives actually make economic differences for their members. Therefore, one of the important research questions in this field is how membership in these cooperatives actually results in improvements in household welfare.

Significance of the Study

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This study is valuable as it provides empirical evidence on how agricultural cooperatives contribute to poverty reduction among rural households in Nepal by enhancing income, employment, and access to financial and agricultural services. Using a before-and-after analysis of key household indicators, it offers deeper insights into changes in welfare after cooperative membership. Focusing on agricultural cooperatives in Hetauda Sub-Metropolitan City, the study also holds practical and policy relevance by informing stakeholders and contributing to research on cooperative-based rural development and sustainable poverty reduction.

Objectives of the study

General Objective:

- To assess changes in poverty status among agricultural cooperative members through a before-and-after analysis of per capita income.

Specific Objectives:

1. To measure the per capita income of cooperative members before and after joining agricultural cooperatives.
2. To examine the per capita expenditure of members before and after joining agricultural cooperatives.

These are the intended objectives to provide empirical evidence on how agricultural cooperatives can enhance the welfare of households and minimize poverty among rural farming communities in Makawanpur District. The results will be beneficial to the academic literature on the topic of cooperative-based rural development and will help policymakers develop more effective cooperative development policies in Nepal.

Hypotheses of the study

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The agricultural cooperatives are supposed to affect the household welfare by the means of better access to credit, agricultural inputs, training opportunities, and collective marketing opportunities. Such institutional services will be able to increase household income, consumption spending, and poverty reduction in rural households. The hypotheses presented below are based on the objective of the study.

H0₁: There is no significant difference in household income before and after joining the agricultural cooperatives.

H0₂: Household expenditure has no considerable difference between pre-membership and post-membership of agricultural cooperatives.

This is the type of objective-hypothesis structure that is prevalent among the econometric and impact assessment researches investigating the manifestations of poverty and cooperative participation (Haughton & Khandker, 2009; Gujarati & Porter, 2009).

In this context, the current study examines the impact of membership in an agricultural cooperative on household poverty in Hetauda, Makawanpur District, Nepal. The study focuses on changes in the welfare of households before and after membership in cooperatives, based on key indicators such as income, expenditure, and household size. Using a before-and-after method, the study aims to provide empirical insights into the extent to which agricultural cooperatives can help reduce rural poverty and improve the standard of living. The findings are expected to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on rural development through cooperatives.

Literature Review

Agricultural cooperatives are well known as such significant institutional arrangements to promote the rural development and alleviate poverty in the developing world (Kwapong & Hanisch, 2013; Verhofstadt & Maertens, 2015). Cooperatives in agrarian economies help smallholder farmers to surmount the market imperfections, such as access to credit, inputs, and markets (Birchall, 2004).

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These institutional provisions improve productivity, generation of incomes and diversification of livelihoods which provide vital channels of reducing poverty. The concept of cooperatives has been actively advocated as a form of development in Nepal, especially since the 1990s, and with a preponderance of advancing agricultural commercialization and rural livelihoods (Dhakal, Brien & Mueser, 2021).

The empirical evidence in Nepal demonstrates that households with cooperative membership have positive impacts on economic outcomes of the household. Indicatively, Dhakal (2022) discovered that the rural household income, savings, and employment enhanced considerably when they participated in farmers cooperatives (Dhakal, 2022). The paper notes that cooperative services like credit access, and collective action has a positive impact on the welfare of the household though the magnitude of the benefits may differ among the members. On the same note, Risal (2021) also came out with the findings that cooperative activities, especially savings mobilization, lending, and creation of employment opportunities are instrumental in promoting sustainable livelihoods and mitigating poverty in Bagmati Province.

Chauguthi et al. (2023) noted that cooperatives help to address poverty through financial inclusion, self-reliance, and income-generation opportunities. According to the findings, they argue that cooperative participation contributes to the sustainability of households and contributes to sustainability in livelihood strategies especially in the rural areas with economic limitations. These results are in line with the evidence in the rest of the world that cooperatives are effective instruments in inclusive economic development and poverty reduction.

Along with the income impacts, agricultural cooperatives also have impact on the agricultural output and agricultural practices. Neupane et al. (2018) discovered that cooperative members in Nepal had more chances of using better agricultural practices and technologies than non-members

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did, resulting in increased productivity and better socio-economic status. High productivity leads to an increase in the household income and consumption expenditure which are major signs of poverty reduction.

Better econometric studies give more information on the effect of cooperative membership. Dhakal and Mueser (2023), based on the propensity score matching, Cooperative membership significant raises the level of farm income, but that effect on overall household income might be contingent on structural characteristics such as landholding size and access to markets. This implies that cooperatives possess positive effects on the economy, but their effects are context-dependent and dependent on other institutional and infrastructural phenomena.

In addition to economic achievements, cooperatives also help to achieve social empowerment and inclusion. Bharti (2021) have investigated that small cooperatives in Nepal contribute to the empowerment of women by increasing their access to credit and decision-making. These social welfares supplement economic wealth and lead to the decrease of multidimensional poverty.

Nevertheless, there are also various issues that the literature recognizes as limitations to the efficacy of cooperatives. Joshi (2024) highlighted poor governance, inaccessibility of capital, and poor management in Nepalese cooperatives, which may negatively affect their performance to provide anticipated economic gains to the members. Such limitation can decrease the net effects.

Nepal's Poverty status

According to the National Statistics Office Nepal, the Nepal Living Standards Survey IV 2022–23 defines the national poverty line based on per capita annual consumption expenditure. An individual in Nepal is considered poor if their annual per capita consumption expenditure is less than NPR 72,908. Using this new poverty threshold, the survey estimates that about 20.27% of Nepal's population lives below the poverty line in 2022–23. Poverty is higher in rural areas

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(24.66%) than in urban areas (18.34%), indicating that rural households remain more vulnerable to poverty. The survey also reports additional poverty indicators, including a poverty gap index of 4.52% and a poverty severity (squared poverty gap) of 1.48%, which measure the depth and inequality of poverty among poor households.

Research Gap

Although many studies have examined the role of agricultural cooperatives in improving livelihoods and financial inclusion, few have used before-and-after analyses to measure their direct impact on household poverty. Most research relies on cross-sectional comparisons, which do not clearly capture changes in welfare after membership. Additionally, limited studies in Nepal, particularly in Hetauda Sub-Metropolitan City—use combined household-level indicators such as per capita income, expenditure, and household size. This study addresses this gap by providing clearer empirical evidence on how cooperative membership influences poverty reduction.

Theoretical Framework

The association between agricultural cooperative membership and household poverty is explicable under a number of theoretical viewpoints that show the institutional participation and its impact on the outcome of household welfare. Cooperatives in rural economies are collective organizations aimed at giving access to smallholder farmers by offering financial services, agricultural inputs and markets. These institutional processes can be used to boost income generation, household consumption, and economic stability. The three theories have been selected as the foundation of this research since the Capability Approach, Social Capital Theory, and Theory of Cooperation in Economies. are considered complementary as they explain how cooperative participation could lead to reduction of poverty among rural households.

Capability Approach

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The Capability Approach, as formulated by Amartya Sen also defines poverty as deprivation of the ability to earn a decent standard of living besides income. These strengths are access to education, economic, financial and social participation. The agricultural cooperatives are able to improve these abilities through giving credit, training, farming inputs, and group marketing. Through such services, the farmers can boost productivity, enhance income and consumption capacity thus enhancing welfare of households (Sen, 1999; Birchall, 2004).

Social Capital Theory

Social Capital Theory focuses on social networks, trust and collective action in advancing economic growth. Becoming a member of cooperatives enhances social relationship among members which promotes information sharing, cooperation and mutual support. These networks enhance access of farmers to knowledge, finances and market. Consequently, cooperative membership may lead to an increase in the welfare of households because of better access to credit, information as well as collective marketing arrangements (Putnam, 1993; Woolcock and Narayan, 2000).

Cooperative Economic Theory

Cooperative Economic Theory is used to describe the functioning of cooperatives as institutions which are member-owned and democratically controlled to enhance the economic wellbeing of members. Cooperatives contribute to solving market failures, cutting transaction costs, and economies of scale by means of collective ownership and pooling resources to farmers. The benefits enhance productivity, bargaining power, raise income and consumption levels within the member households. Agricultural cooperatives in Nepal are relevant to rural farmers because they assist in accessing the financial market and financial inclusion that result in poverty reduction and economic resilience (Birchall, 2004; International Labour Organization, 2015).

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Application to the Study

According to these theoretical views, agricultural cooperative membership will have an effect on household welfare in the form of better access to financial services, inputs, and markets. These advancements are able to raise the household income, consumption /expenditure and the overall living standard which in the long run influences the status of household poverty. This paper will study how cooperative membership in agricultural cooperatives can alleviate house hold poverty by comparing the changes in this indicator before and after membership in the cooperatives in the Hetauda Sub-Metropolitan City, Makawanpur District, Nepal.

Review of Empirical Literature

Yang and Hung (2014) explored the role of tourism cooperatives in poverty alleviation in Yuhu Village, China, using a qualitative case study approach. Based on interviews with villagers and cooperative managers, the study found that tourism cooperatives reduced poverty by enhancing material and social resources and empowering local residents. It concluded that such cooperatives are effective when poverty is viewed multidimensionally, though the study did not address long-term economic impacts or comparisons with other approaches.

Lal (2018) examined the impact of financial inclusion through cooperative banks on poverty alleviation in northern India using a quantitative approach. Based on data from 540 beneficiaries analyzed through techniques such as CFA, ANOVA, t-test, and SEM, the study found that improved access to financial services, savings, credit, and insurance, significantly reduced poverty and enhanced rural socio-economic conditions. However, the study was limited in geographical scope and did not include perspectives from other stakeholders.

Zhang et al. (2021) investigated the impact of cooperative irrigation schemes on poverty reduction in Tanzania using a quantitative approach. Based on survey data analyzed through regression and poverty measurement techniques, the study found that participants achieved higher productivity, increased income, and reduced poverty compared to non-participants. It concluded that irrigation

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cooperatives significantly improved livelihoods, though the study was limited to irrigation schemes and did not address broader forms of agricultural cooperatives.

Gava et al. (2021) examined the role of agricultural cooperatives in alleviating rural poverty in Konjic, Bosnia and Herzegovina, using a mixed-method case study design. Data from cooperative members and stakeholders, collected through questionnaires, interviews, and secondary sources, showed that cooperatives enhanced market access, increase farm income, and strengthen farmer collaboration. The study concluded that cooperatives contributed significantly to rural development, though it lacked large-scale quantitative comparisons between members and non-members.

Zou and Wang (2022) examined the impact of farmer cooperative membership on household income and inequality in China using a quantitative approach based on data from 1,945 rural households. Applying PSM and regression techniques, the study found that cooperative members had higher average income, though benefits were less significant for low-income groups. It concluded that while cooperatives increase income, they do not necessarily reduce inequality, and other influencing factors were not fully considered.

Khairil et al. (2025) investigated the role of sharia cooperatives in alleviating poverty in Aceh using a qualitative descriptive literature review based on over 25 academic sources. The findings showed that sharia cooperatives reduced poverty by offering inclusive financial services, generating employment, supporting micro and small enterprises, and enhancing social solidarity, highlighting their potential to improve community welfare and achieve sustainable development goals.

Sari et al. (2026) examined the role of agricultural cooperatives in farmer empowerment and poverty reduction through a qualitative literature review of 157 Scopus-indexed articles (2005–2024) using PRISMA guidelines. The study found that cooperatives enhanced farmers' income,

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social networks, and access to markets, finance, and technology, thereby contributing to poverty reduction.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The research was conducted in Hetauda Sub-Metropolitan City, an agricultural area of central Nepal. The region practices mixed farming, including crop cultivation, livestock rearing, and vegetable production. Agricultural cooperatives in this area provide services such as savings and credit, farm inputs, technical training, and marketing support to smallholder farmers. These services enhance productivity and market access, making the area suitable for examining the impact of cooperative membership on household poverty.

Research Design and Data Sources

This study employed a cross-section survey research design which used before-and-after comparative approach to make before-and-after assessment of per capita income among agricultural cooperative members to determine their poverty status in the Hetauda Sub-Metropolitan City of Makawanpur District, Nepal. It compared household economic conditions before and after joining cooperatives, a common approach in development economics to measure institutional effects on welfare (Haugh & Khandker, 2009). Both primary and secondary data were used. Primary data were collected from cooperative members in 2025 through structured questionnaires covering household income, expenditure, and size before and after membership. Secondary data included cooperative records, government publications, and relevant academic literature on cooperatives and poverty.

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

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The study sample consisted of members from five agricultural cooperatives operating in Hetauda Sub-Metropolitan City. Respondents were selected using simple random sampling from the membership lists of the targeted cooperatives. A total of 123 members participated in the survey out of 180 members.

Measurement of Variables

Household poverty was measured using three key indicators: income, expenditure, and household size. Household income reflects earnings from agricultural and non-agricultural activities, while expenditure indicates consumption and living standards. Household size serves as a demographic factor influencing resource allocation and dependency (World Bank, 2009). These indicators were assessed both before and after cooperative membership to evaluate changes in household welfare.

Data Analysis and Statistical tools

The collected data were analyzed using SPSS with both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics, including frequency, mean, percentage, and standard deviation, summarized respondents' socio-economic characteristics and changes in household income, expenditure, and size. To test whether cooperative membership significantly influenced household welfare, a paired sample t-test was applied, comparing income and expenditure before and after joining the cooperatives (Gujarati & Porter, 2009).

Table 1

Description of Minimum, Maximum, Mean and Standard Deviation

Variables	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Cooperative membership duration of the respondents	1	15	7.32	3.972
Number of household member	3	9	5.13	1.708
Now, your family annual income in Rs.	100000	2000000	627398.37	310493.62

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Now, your family annual expenditure in Rs.	150000	1500000	435284.55	200312.56
Your Family annual income before involving in agriculture cooperatives in Rs.	100000	1000000	361300.81	139837.19
Your Family annual expenditure before involving in agriculture cooperatives in Rs.	100000	5000000	293780.49	440051.851
Current Per capita income of household members	25000.00	250000.00	124946.18	48563.29
Current Per capita expenditure of household members	33333.33	187500.00	87518.48	33902.59
Per capita income of household members before membership	12500.00	233333.33	75878.56	33905.72
Per capita expenditure of household members before membership	11111.11	714285.71	59215.35	64641.05

Valid N (listwise) 123

Above descriptive statistics shows that the average per capita annual income and expenditure, before and after membership of cooperative was increased from NPR Rs.124946 to NPR Rs.75856. Per capita average expenditure of household members also increased which indicate that consumption capacity and living standard of cooperative members were improved.

Examine the (H_0) household income before and after joining the agricultural cooperatives.

Table 2

Comparison of Per capita income After and before membership

Variable	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Per capita income of household members after membership	124946.1866	123	48563.29229	4378.80460
Per capita income of household members before membership	75878.5650	123	33905.72528	3057.17629

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According to descriptive statistics, average household per capita income significantly increased but there was variation in income level but the relatively small standard error of mean indicate that the sample mean estimates were reliable.

On the whole, descriptive statistics indicate that the agricultural cooperatives membership played the role of increasing the per capita income of the household members which justifies the point that cooperatives are significant in improving the livelihood of the rural people and alleviating poverty.

Table 3

Pair Samples T-Test of Before and After per Capita Income

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Current Per capita income of household members - Per capita income of household members before membership	49067.62	48637.76	4385.51	40386.04	57749.19	11.189	122	.000

The results show that the average current per capita household income was NPR 124,946.19, which was much higher than the average income before joining agricultural cooperatives (NPR 75,878.57). This suggests that the income level of members improved after they joined the cooperative.

The standard deviation values indicate that income levels varied among households in both periods. However, the relatively small standard error means the sample averages were reliable.

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Overall, these results suggest that agricultural cooperative membership helped increase the per capita income of households, supporting the idea that cooperatives contribute to improving rural livelihoods and reducing poverty. It rejected the null hypothesis. It means there was a significant difference in household income before and after joining the agricultural cooperatives.

Table 4

Comparison of Per Capita Expenditure After and Before Membership

Variables	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Per capita expenditure of household members after membership	87518.48	123	33902.59	3056.89
Per capita expenditure of household members before membership	59215.35	123	64641.05	5828.48

The results show that the average per capita household expenditure after joining the cooperative was NPR 87,518.48, which was higher than the average expenditure before membership (NPR 59,215.35). This suggests that household spending increased after becoming cooperative members. The standard deviation indicates that expenditure varies among households in both periods. Overall, the increase in average expenditure suggests an improvement in the living standards of cooperative members after joining the cooperative.

Table 5

Pair Samples T-Test of Per Capita Expenditure After and Before Membership

Paired Differences	t	df
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Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		Sig. (2-tailed)
				Lower	Upper	
Current Per capita expenditure of household members - Per capita expenditure of household members before membership	28303.13	64071.19	5777.10	16866.77	39739.49	4.899 122 .000

The results show that the average increase in per capita household expenditure after joining the cooperative was NPR 28,303.13. The t-value (4.899) with 122 degrees of freedom was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), which means the increase was not due to chance. The 95% confidence interval (16,866.77 to 39,739.49) also confirms that expenditure increased after membership. Overall, this suggests that households spent more after joining agricultural cooperatives, indicating an improvement in their living standards. It rejected the null hypothesis. It shows that household expenditure had considerable difference between pre-membership and post-membership of agricultural cooperatives.

Results and Discussion

The results show that the mean per capita income of respondents increased from 75,878.565 before membership to 124,946.186 after membership. The paired samples t-test value ($p = .000$) indicates that this increase was statistically significant, suggesting that cooperative membership had a strong positive effect on improving income.

Similarly, the mean per capita expenditure rose from 59,215.35 before membership to 87,518.48 after membership. The paired samples t-test value ($p = .000$) also shows a statistically significant

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difference. It indicates that respondents' spending capacity improved after joining the cooperative.

This result is consistent with the findings of Sari et al. (2026), who reported that agricultural cooperatives enhanced farmers' income and reduce poverty through improved access to markets, finance, and technology. Similarly, Khairil et al. (2025) supported these findings by highlighting that cooperative improved community welfare through financial inclusion and employment generation.

The increase in income observed in this study also aligned with Lal (2018) and Zhang et al. (2021), who found that access to financial services and cooperative participation significantly improved income and livelihoods. Likewise, Gava et al. (2021) reported that cooperatives increased farm income and strengthen rural economies, which corresponds with the observed rise in both income and expenditure in this study.

However, while Zou and Wang (2022) found that cooperative membership increased income but did not equally benefit all income groups, the present study generally shows an overall positive effect without differentiating across income levels. In addition, Yang and Hung (2014) emphasized multidimensional poverty reduction through empowerment and social resources, which complements the present findings by suggesting that increased income and expenditure may also reflect broader socio-economic improvements. Furthermore, Bhattarai and Pandit (2023) highlighted the supportive role of cooperatives in agricultural development, although they lacked empirical income evidence, which the present study helps to substantiate.

The present findings strongly support previous studies, confirming that cooperative membership significantly improves income, expenditure, and overall economic well-being, while also contributing empirical evidence to the existing literature.

Conclusion

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The study analysis has revealed that agricultural cooperative membership has helped in bettering the economic status of households in Hetauda Sub-Metropolitan City, Makawanpur District. The descriptive statistics, paired sample tests indicate that per capita household income, as well as per capita household expenditure, has risen significantly following membership of agricultural cooperatives. The statistically significant findings imply that collaborative membership has been key in enhancing the financial ability and standards of living of member households. As can also be seen in the correlation analysis, poverty status pre- and post-membership in the cooperative has a positive and significant correlation, which is to say that poor households at the time of membership are slightly more likely to keep being poor even after membership. Nevertheless, the correlation is moderate which means that there were households who managed to gain better economic status having become cooperative members. The outcome also indicates that the household size was significantly related to poverty status prior to cooperative membership but did not relate with poverty status after cooperative membership, which implies that cooperative membership can be used to minimize the adverse economic effects of having a large household. Besides this, the length of time of the membership of the respondents does not indicate any significant relationship with poverty status, meaning that the longer one is a member the more likely that the poverty status will be reduced. The results indicate that agricultural cooperatives are beneficial in increasing household income, consumption level, and maintaining livelihoods of rural communities, yet it might not fully alleviate poverty among all the members. Thus, empowering agricultural cooperatives by providing better financial services, training and market access would help to further increase contribution of agricultural cooperatives to poverty reduction and rural development in Nepal.

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